

Lightning Protector Cap

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The design for lightning protector cap is given in the picture. It consist mainly seven part namely A, B,C,D,E,F,G.

A: Pointed conductor.(Length 6 inch)

B: Plate of conductor(radius 5 inch)

C: 16 gauge conducting wire insulated by thick insulator.

D: Nonconducting stick of length of length 1 ft

E: Sensor or indicator

F: Cap of insulator(radius 1ft)

G: Plate of conductor which will be grounded

Working Principle: When charged cloud appears above the cap, the pointed conductor minimizes charge of cloud as much as possible by the discharging action of of pointed conductor.so, the probability of lightning become less. But , still there is some probability for lightning, and the lightning will occur between cloud and pointed conductor.

Current follow the low resistance path, so, the current due to lightning must reach to the ground through A,B,C and G.

The nonconducting stick(D) and cap(F) insulated the farmer head from current due to lightning.

In presence of charge (due to induction of cloud charge) on the pointed conductor ,the indicator made sound to alert the farmer .

When indicator make sound, the farmer must rises his/her hands from soil or water.

The farmer must ware a thick rubber leg glabs . By some way, plate g is attached with farmer foot i.e grounded .